

Supplementary table 2. Origin and database of articles selected to compose a systematic review on improvement of banana to Fusarium wilt.

Article	Journal	Insertion in START Program
Ahmad et. al 2020	Theoretical and Applied Genetics	Manually
Arinaitwe et. al 2019	Euphytica	Manually
Azam et. al 2017	Journal of Plant Biochemistry & Physiology	Google Acadêmico
Baharum et. al 2018	Sains Malaysiana	Web of Science
Bai et. al 2013	PLoS ONE	PubMed Central
Buregyeya et. al 2020	Journal of Plant Breeding and Crop Science	Manually
Chandrasekaran et. al 2019	Agronomy	Web of Science
Chen et. al 2012	Plant Pathology	Web of Science
Chen et. al 2019	Frontiers in Microbiology	Web of Science
Cheng et. al 2018	BMC Genomic	PubMed Central
Cheng et. al 2019	Scientific Reports	Manually
Cunha et. al 2015	Scientia Horticulturae	Web of Science
Dale et. al 2017	Nature communications	PubMed Central
Dong et. al 2016	Environmental and Experimental Botany	Web of Science
Dong et. al 2019	Phytopathology	Manually
Dou et. al 2020	Plant Biotechnology journal	Manually
Fan et. al 2019	Journal of Plant Pathology	Web of Science
Fei et. al 2019	Phytopathology Research	Manually
Garcez et. al 2016	Bioscience Journal Uberlândia	Web of Science
García-Bastidas et. al 2019	Frontiers in Plant Science	Manually
Ghag et. al 2012	PLoS ONE	Web of Science
Ghag et. al 2014a	Plant Cell Tiss Organ Cult	Web of Science
Ghag et. al 2014b	Plant Biotechnology journal	Web of Science
Ghag et. al 2014c	AoB PLANTS	PubMed Central
Ghag et. al 2014d	Mol Biol Rep	Scopus
Ghag et. al 2015	Current Trends in Biotechnology and Pharmacy	Manually
Gonçalves et. al 2019	Eur J Plant Pathol	Manually
Hu et. al 2013	In Vitro Cell.Dev.Biol.-Plant	Google Acadêmico
Huang et. al 2010	Plant Mol Biol Rep	Google Acadêmico
Karmawan et. al 2018	Archives of Phytopathology and Plant Protection	Google Acadêmico
Kishor et. al 2018	Int.J.Curr.Microbiol.App.Sci	Google Acadêmico
Kotari et. al 2018	Australasian Plant Disease Notes	Web of Science
Krishna et. al 2013	Indian Journal of Experimental Biology	Google Acadêmico
Li et. al 2011a	Eur J Plant Pathol	Web of Science
Li et. al 2011b	African Journal of Biotechnology	Web of Science

Li et. al 2012	BMC Genomics	PubMed Central
Li et. al 2013a	BMC Genomics	Springer
Li et. al 2013b	Proteome Science	Google Acadêmico
Li et. al 2015a	Plant pathology	Web of Science
Li et. al 2015b	Euphytica	Portal Periódicos CAPES
Li et. al 2017a	Scientific Reports	Web of Science
Li et. al 2017b	Plant Disease	Web of Science
Liu et. al 2010	Journal of Integrative Plant Biology	Web of Science
Lu et. al 2013	Physiological and Molecular Plant Pathology	Web of Science
Luo et. al 2016	Journal of Integrative Agriculture	Web of Science
Ma et. al 2013	Journal of Experimental Botany	PubMed Central
Magambo et. al 2016	African Journal of Biotechnology	Google Acadêmico
Mintoff et. al 2019	Australian Bananas Magazine	Manually
Mohandas et. al 2013	Scientia Horticulturae	Web of Science
Munusamy et. al 2019	Pak. J. Agri. Sci.	Web of Science
Nasir et. al 2016	International Journal on Advanced Science	Google Acadêmico
Niu et. al 2018	International Journal of Molecular Science	PubMed Central
Orr et. al 2019	Australasian Plant Disease Notes	Web of Science
Paul et. al 2011	Plant Biotechnology Journal	Web of Science
Ramu et. al 2016	Proteomes	Google Acadêmico
Ribeiro et. al 2018	Revista Brasileira de Fruticultura	Web of Science
Rocha et. al 2020	Eur J Plant Pathol	Manually
Saraswathi et. al 2016	Indian Journal of Experimental Biology	Scopus
Silva et. al 2016	Genetics and Molecular Research	Web of Science
Smith et. al 2014	Scientia Horticulturae	Web of Science
Smith et. al 2018	Crop Protection	Google Acadêmico
Song et. al 2016	South African Journal of Botany	Manually
Song et. al 2018	PeerJ	Web of Science
Ssali et. al 2013	Euphytica	Portal Periódicos CAPES
Subramaniam et. al 2010	Tree and Forestry Science and Biotechnology	Google Acadêmico
Sun et. al 2010	Molecular Plant Breeding	Google Acadêmico
Sun et. al 2011	African Journal of Microbiology Research	Web of Science
Sun et. al 2013	Scientia Horticulturae	Google Acadêmico
Sun et. al 2019	Plant Physiology and Biochemistry	Google Acadêmico
Sunisha et. al 2020	Molecular Biotechnology	Manually
Sutanto et. al 2014	Emir. J. Food Agric.	Google Acadêmico
Swarupa et. al 2013	Physiological and Molecular Plant Pathology	Web of Science
Thakker et. al 2013	ISRN Biotechnology	PubMed Central

Ting et. al 2012	Biological Control	Web of Science
Waman et. al 2018	Erwerbs-Obstbau	Portal Periódicos CAPES
Wang et. al 2012a	BMC Genomics	PubMed Central
Wang et. al 2012b	Mol Biol Rep	Google Acadêmico
Wang et. al 2015a	Acta Physiol Plant	Web of Science
Wang et. al 2015b	Funct Integr Genomics	Web of Science
Wang et. al 2016a	Biologia Plantarum	Web of Science
Wang et. al 2016b	South African Journal of Botany	Web of Science
Wang et. al 2017	Canadian Journal of Plant Pathology	Google Acadêmico
Wang et. al 2018	Not Bot Horti Agrob	Google Acadêmico
Warman and Aitken 2018	Frontiers in Plant Science	Web of Science
Wei et. al 2016	J. Pineal Res	Web of Science
Wei et. al 2017a	Plant Cell Rep	Springer
Wu et. al 2010	Eur J Plant Pathol	Web of Science
Wu et. al 2013	Journal of Plant Physiology	Google Acadêmico
Wu et. al 2017	Scientific Reports	PubMed Central
Yip et. al 2011	Plant Biotechnol Rep	Springer
Zhang et. al 2017	Journal of Phytopathology	Web of Science
Zhang et. al 2018	Euphytica	Web of Science
Zhang et. al 2019	Scientific Reports	Google Acadêmico
Zhang et. al 2020	Proteome Science	Manually
Zuo et. al 2018	Eur J Plant Pathol	Web of Science

START: State of the Art through Systematic Review; CAPES: Coordination for the Improvement of Higher Education Personnel.